

Industrial Robot Solution by ANFIS

Gurjeet Singh , V. K. Banga

Research Scholar I.KG Punjab Technical University [1], Professor & Principal ,ACET, Amritsar[2]

Email: - mann_567@yahoo.com,vijaykumr.banga@gmail.com

Abstract— In this paper Inverse kinematics solution of the PUMA 560 is solved. In robotics the main problem is to find the inverse kinematics solution. Forward kinematics is calculated with the help of D-H (Denavit-Hartenberg) parameter method. Now a day's inverse kinematics is the area of research in robotics. In present paper, Inverse kinematics is calculated by mathematically and by ANFIS and then difference between the predicted value and deducted value is calculated. Workspace area of PUMA Robot is also shown in this paper.

Keywords— ANFIS, kinematics, Robotics arm, optimization, Robot manipulator, Neural networks, Fuzzy logic.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advancement of technology robots play an important role in the Industry. PUMA robot used in different industries for safety reasons. It also increase the production in the industries. The efficiency and the accuracy of the industries also improve

with the use of the robots[1].

Now a days, study of robotics is a new topic of research .This

study of robotics is done with the help of kinematics, In robotics there are forward and inverse kinematics[11]. As the degree of

freedom increase in the robot it's very difficult to find the solution of Inverse kinematics [12]. The forward kinematics is solved with the help of Denavit-Hartenberg (D-H) parameter. PUMA 560 is a six degree of freedom robots and each link is shown in the figure[1].

Figure1. Puma 560 robot[4]

Many techniques are used to calculate the solution of inverse kinematics like algebraic, geometric and numerical method. In this paper the inverse kinematics solution is find out by the D-H parameter and code is written in the MATLAB ,the same solution is find out by the applying the adaptive neuro fuzzy interface system(ANFIS)[3].

II. D-H PARAMETER

D-H parameters are nearly new to calculate the kinematics solution of the robots. There are the four parameters used in this which define the relationship between the joints[13].

The parameters are shown below in table. In forward kinematics the theta values are given and the values of x,y,z are find out. In each robot the first step is to find the forward kinematics using the table[5].

θ_i	a_i	d_i	α_i
90	-90	0	-160 to +160
0	0	149.09	-225 to 45
90	90	0	-45 to 225
0	-90	433.07	-110 to 170
0	90	0	-100 to 100
0	0	56.25	-266 to 266

Table 1: DH Parameter of PUMA 560 Robot

$$T = T_1 T_2 T_3 T_4 T_5 T_6 = {}^0A_1 {}^1A_2 {}^2A_3 {}^3A_4 {}^4A_5 {}^5A_6 = \begin{bmatrix} n_x & s_x & a_x & p_x \\ n_y & s_y & a_y & p_y \\ n_z & s_z & a_z & p_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$n_{x1} = C_1 [C_{23}(C_4 C_5 C_6 - S_4 S_6) - S_{23} S_5 C_6] - S_1 (S_4 C_5 C_6 + C_4 S_6) \quad (1)$$

$$n_{y1} = S_1 [C_{23}(C_4 C_5 C_6 - S_4 S_6) - S_{23} S_5 C_6] + C_1 (S_4 C_5 C_6 + C_4 S_6) \quad (2)$$

$$n_{z1} = -S_{23} [C_4 C_5 C_6 - S_4 S_6] - C_{23} S_5 C_6 \quad (3)$$

$$s_{x1} = C_1 [-C_{23}(C_4 C_5 C_6 + S_4 S_6) + S_{23} S_5 C_6] - S_1 (-S_4 C_5 C_6 + C_4 S_6) \quad (4)$$

$$s_{y1} = S_1 [-C_{23}(C_4 C_5 C_6 + S_4 S_6) + S_{23} S_5 C_6] + C_1 (-S_4 C_5 C_6 + C_4 S_6) \quad (5)$$

$$s_{z1} = S_{23} [C_4 C_5 C_6 + S_4 S_6] - C_{23} S_5 C_6 \quad (6)$$

$$a_{x1} = C_1 [C_{23} C_4 S_5 + S_{23} C_5] - S_1 S_4 S_5 \quad (7)$$

$$a_{y1} = S_1 [C_{23} C_4 S_5 + S_{23} C_5] - C_1 S_4 S_5 \quad (8)$$

$$a_{z1} = -S_{23} C_4 S_5 + C_{23} C_5 \quad (9)$$

$$p_{x1} = C_1 [d_6 (C_{23} C_4 S_5 + S_{23} C_5) + S_{23} d_4 + C_{23} a_3 + C_2 a_2] - S_1 (d_6 S_4 S_5 + d_2) \quad (10)$$

$$p_{y1} = S_1 [d_6 (C_{23} C_4 S_5 + S_{23} C_5) + S_{23} d_4 + C_{23} a_3 + C_2 a_2] + C_1 (d_6 S_4 S_5 + d_2) \quad (11)$$

$$p_{z1} = d_6 (C_{23} C_5 - S_{23} C_4 S_5) + C_{23} d_4 - S_{23} a_3 - S_2 a_2 \quad (12)$$

[16]

Inverse Kinematics

After finding the forward kinematics the next step is to calculate

different thetas. Inverse kinematics is a important thing in the robotics and to find the best theta values is a important thing[6][14].

$$\theta_1 = \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{P^2 + d^2} - \sqrt{P_x^2 + P_y^2 + d^2}}{P_x + P_y + d_2} \quad (13)$$

all the possible values of the arm and the elbow is shown in Table 2

$$\sin(\theta_2) = \sin \alpha_1 \cos \beta_1 + (\text{ARM1.ELBOW1}) \cos \alpha \sin \beta \quad (14)$$

$$\cos(\theta_2) = \cos \alpha \cos \beta - (\text{ARM1.ELBOW1}) \sin \alpha \sin \beta \quad (15)$$

$$\theta_2 = \tan^{-1} \frac{\sin(\theta_2)}{\cos(\theta_2)} \quad (16)$$

$$R = \sqrt{\frac{P_x^2 + P_y^2 + P_z^2 - d^2}{2}} \quad (17)$$

$$\cos \phi = \frac{a_2^2 + (d_4^2 + a_3^2) - R^2}{2 a_2 \sqrt{d^2 + a^2}} \quad (18)$$

$$\sin(\phi) = \text{ARM.ELBOW} \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \phi} \quad (19)$$

$$\sin \beta = \frac{d_4}{\sqrt{d^2 + a^2}} \quad (20)$$

$$\cos \beta = \frac{a_3}{\sqrt{d^2 + a^2}} \quad (21)$$

$$\sin(\theta_3) = \sin \phi \cos \beta + \cos \phi \sin \beta \quad (22)$$

$$\cos(\theta_3) = \cos \phi \cos \beta + \sin \phi \sin \beta \quad (23)$$

$$\theta_3 = \tan^{-1} \frac{\sin(\theta_3)}{\cos(\theta_3)} \quad (24)$$

Table. 3 represent the wrist orientation.

$$\theta_4 = \tan^{-1} \frac{M(C_1 a_y - S_1 a_x)}{M(C_1 a_x C_{23} + C_{23} S_1 a_y - S_{23} a_z)} \quad (25)$$

$$\theta_5 = \tan^{-1} \frac{(C_1 C_{23} C_4 - S_1 S_4) a_x + (S_1 C_{23} C_4 + C_1 S_4) a_y - C_4 S_{23} a_z}{(C_1 S_{23} a_x + S_1 S_{23} C_4 a_y + C_{23} a_z)} \quad (26)$$

$$\theta_6 = \tan^{-1} \frac{(-C_1 C_{23} C_4 - S_1 C_4) n_x + (-S_1 C_{23} S_4 + C_1 C_4) n_y - S_4 S_{23} n_z}{(-C_1 C_{23} C_4 - S_1 C_4) s_x + (-S_1 C_{23} S_4 + C_1 C_4) s_y - S_4 S_{23} s_z} \quad (27)$$

Arm Configuration	ARM	ELBOW	ARM.ELBOW
Port side and up	-1	+1	-1
Port side and down	-1	-1	+1
upRight and up	+1	+1	+1
upRight and down	+1	-1	-1

Table 2: Various arm configuration for joint 2

III. ADAPTIVE NUERO- FUZZY INTERFACE SYSTEM(ANFIS)

It is a rule based method also called a hybrid learning

procedure; it is a amalgam of the neural network and the fuzzy logic.[7] This techniques discovered in 1990 based on Takagi–Sugeno fuzzy inference system.The fuzzy logic considered the imprecision and uncertainty while neural network give the sense of adaptability[8]. The training is done with the help of the input output datasets. The main objective of ANFIS is to built a model of robotics on which fuzzy rules are applied to get the input–output dataset[9].

Fuzzy interfece model approximate the data set consist of collection of input-output.Such models have a number of membership function with adjustable parameter[10]. The

neuro adbtative learning take place through input output

dataset and using this database anfis construct a fuzzy interference structure whose parameters are adjusted with

the backpropogation and least square method. The parameters of the membership function adjusted or changed as the learning process is going on.

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The methodoly used in this process is shown below. In this first the D-H parameter of the robot is used to calculate the Kinematics result of the robot. The matlab code is written for these equation and these values called the analytical values. Now using the anfis technique the solution of inverse kinematics is find out this value is called as predicted value. For anfis we given the value of

membership function ,number of epochs ,and other parameter. Then the both values are compared.

Methodology

Wriest Orientation	Ω= s.y5	Wrist	M= Wrist*Ω
Declining	≥0	+1	+1

Figure3: Divergence of the predicted and analytical value

The ANFIS procedure followed is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: ANFIS Procedure

In figure 5 the ANFIS procedure is shown in which first we open anfis tool and initialize the fuzzy system then set the number of iteration and the input data is taken from the workspace and then start the learning process. The data is validate in the end. The figure 5 show the training of the six theta values by ANFIS network the co-ordinates will act as a input and the different theta values will act as a output. The membership function of the model is adjust so that it will give a best theta values as output.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 5: Training result of different theta(1to6) by ANFIS

The work space area of PUMA 560 arm) is shown below .The red star show the resolution and in this area the movement of the robot is fine and the resolution of the end effectors is maximum.

Figure 6. Workspace Area of PUMA 560

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper the solution of Inverse kinematics problem of PUMA robot is find out by by using ANFIS technique and joint angles are derived for the trajectory. The difference between the analytical and the predicted value is calculated and the results are acceptable.

As compared to the other techniques this technique is acceptable and produces fast result of inverse kinematics. The workspace area of the end effector of a robot is also shown in a figure.

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